

Compound extremes: impacts of climate change and socioeconomic development

Takumi Therville, University of Antwerp

Table of content

1. Climate change and compound events
2. Socio-economic development and compound events
3. Future perspectives

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Climate change and compound events

(Zscheischler, J., et al. 2020)

3 ways compound events are impacted by climate change :

- **Mean shifts**

Fig 6 from Zscheischler, J., et al. (2020)

Climate change and compound events

(Zscheischler, J., et al. 2020)

3 ways compound events are impacted by climate change :

- Mean shifts
- Variance shifts

Fig 6 from Zscheischler, J., et al. (2020)

Climate change and compound events

(Zscheischler, J., et al. 2020)

3 ways compound events are impacted by climate change :

- Mean shifts
- Variance shifts
- Dependence shifts

Fig 6 from Zscheischler, J., et al. (2020)

Refresher morning session

(Zscheischler, J., et al. 2020)

Preconditioning compounds	Temporal compounds
Spatial compounds	Multivariate compounds

Table of content

1. Climate change and compound events
 - a) Multivariate compounds
 - b) Temporal compounds
 - c) Spatial compounds
2. Socio-economic development and compound events
3. Future perspectives

Trend historical compounds

(Ridder, N.N., et al. 2020)

Compound events related to wet conditions

Trend historical compounds : Importance of regional datasets

(Ridder, N.N., et al. 2020)

High precipitation
and wind

FFDI and drought

Compound flooding

(McGrath, B.M., 2019)

Climate change and multivariate compounds : extreme meteorological tides and precipitation

(Bevacqua, E., et al. 2020)

Joint return period change between future (2070-2099) and baseline (1970-2004) climate.

Climate change and multivariate compounds : extreme meteorological tides and precipitation

(Bevacqua, E., et al. 2020)

(a) Precipitation-related return period change

(c) Meteorological-tide-related return period change

Climate change and multivariate compounds : Extreme meteorological tides and precipitation

(Bevacqua, E., et al. 2020)

(e) Dependence-related return period change

Compound hot-dry events

(Hao, Z., et al. 2022)

Climate change and multivariate compounds : compound hot-dry events

(Tabari, H. & Willems, P., 2023)

Difference in CMIP6 ensemble median frequency between the 2061–2100 and 1971–2010 periods.

Compound hot-dry events and the choice of univariate

(Hosseinzadehtalaei, P., Termonia, P. & Tabari, H., 2024)

Compound hot-dry events and the choice of univariate

(Hosseinzadehtalaei, P., Termonia, P. & Tabari, H., 2024)

Contribution to total uncertainty in projected changes in the probability of compound hot-dry events

Table of content

1. Climate change and compound events
 - a) Multivariate compounds
 - b) Temporal compounds
 - c) Spatial compounds
2. Socio-economic development and compound events
3. Future perspectives

Precipitation whiplash (under review)

Precipitation whiplash (under review)

Precipitation whiplash

(Tan, X. et al., 2023)

Dry-to-wet

frequency

global and land mean of frequency

— CESM-LENS-global — CHIRPS — REGEN_LongTermStns — MERRA2
 - - CESM-LENS-land — GPCP — ERA5 — JRA-55

Wet-to-dry

frequency

global and land mean of frequency

Projected relative change (%) in occurrence frequency of precipitation whiplash in the last four decades of the 21st Century (2060–2099) under the RCP8.5 forcing relative to the current period (1979–2019)

Precipitation whiplash

(Tan, X. et al., 2023)

Global area-weighted average of occurrence frequency of dry-to-wet whiplash derived from the ensembles of CESM-LENS (yellow), all-but-no industrial aerosols (XAERs, cyan), all-but-no greenhouse gases (XGHGs, green), and all-but-no biomass burning aerosols (XBMB, purple)

Table of content

1. Climate change and compound events
 - a) Multivariate compounds
 - b) Temporal compounds
 - c) Spatial compounds
2. Socio-economic development and compound events
3. Future perspectives

Spatial drought

Agricultural drought risk situation from 21/09/2024-30/09/2024 from the global drought observatory

Climate change and spatial compounds

Large scale atmospheric patterns impact the climate in remote areas around the globe. E.g., ENSO (El Niño-Southern Oscillation).

NOAA schematic diagrams, accessed 01/08/2025

Climate change and spatial compounds : ENSO

EL NIÑO CLIMATE IMPACTS

December-February

LA NIÑA CLIMATE IMPACTS

December-February

NOAA (2016), accessed 01/08/2025

Resource for ENSO impacts on Europe :
<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/COPSRV/ENSO+impacts+on+Europe>

Climate change and spatial compounds :

Concurrent drought events (Singh, J. et al., 2022)

Climate change and spatial compounds : Concurrent drought events (Singh, J. et al., 2022)

Agriculture area and population exposure risk to severe compound drought

Table of content

1. Climate change and compound events
2. Socio-economic development and compound events
 - a) Land use change
 - b) Risk framework
3. Future perspectives

Urbanization and compound heat and precipitation

(Wu, S., et al., 2021)

Urbanization and compound heat and precipitation

(Wu, S., et al., 2021)

Land use change and compound warm-wet events

(Camara, M., Diba, I., & Diedhiou, A., 2022)

- Two climate model runs.
- One control run,
 - One with a modified land use : Reforestation of the Sahel-Sahara interface

Land use change and compound warm-wet events

(Camara, M., Diba, I., & Diedhiou, A., 2022)

Land use change and compound warm-wet events

(Camara, M., Diba, I., & Diedhiou, A., 2022)

a. Wet/Warm JJAS RegCM4_CTL

b. Wet/Warm JJAS RegCM4_REFORESTATION

c. Diff JJAS RegCM4_REFORESTA – RegCM4_CTL

Risk framework (IPCC AR5)

Risk and compound hot-dry events

(Tabari, H., Willems, P, 2023)

Future perspectives – Climate change

- New compound events
- Uncertainty analysis
- Resolution of climate models

Future perspectives : Climate change – emerging compounds

(Matthews, T., et al., 2019)

Historical asynchrony of Heat Index (HI, red) peaks and Tropical Cyclone (TC, blue) season across major TC regions.

Future perspectives : Climate change – emerging compounds

(Matthews, T., et al., 2019)

Historical 121 major TC tracks (blue),
red shows the 4 major TCs followed by
a HI of 40.6 or more within 30 days of
landfall

Future perspectives : Climate change – emerging compounds

(Matthews, T., et al., 2019)

Major probable TC tracks (with at least a 50% chance of experiencing HI40.6 in the 30 days following landfall) for various levels of global warming: baseline (a), 1.5 °C (b), 2.0 °C (c) and 4.0 °C. Dotted blue lines show potential TC tracks (with non-zero probability of being followed by HI40.6).

Future perspectives – Climate change

- New compound events
- Uncertainty analysis
- Resolution of climate models

Future perspectives – Climate change

- New compound events
- Uncertainty analysis
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Future perspectives – Socio-economic development

- Resolution of climate models
- Risk assessments
- Adaptation and mitigation

Future perspectives – Socio-economic development

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Risk framework (IPCC AR5)

Future perspectives – Socio-economic development

- Resolution of climate models
- Risk assessments
- Adaptation and mitigation

Risk framework (IPCC AR6)

Thank you for your attention !

University of Antwerp
M4S |
Modelling For Sustainability

Takumi Therville
Modelling for Sustainability (M4S)
University of Antwerp, Belgium
takumi.Therville@uantwerpen.be

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